

PEDAGOGICAL AND COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES IN THE WORK OF A TEACHER

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Abstract: In this article, I once again emphasize the need to train future teachers as cultural individuals, armed with high pedagogical skills and technical skills. Human abilities are considered as an opportunity to acquire knowledge and skills. He deeply revealed the qualitative characteristics of abilities and features of teaching abilities.

Key words: abilities, ability, ability, talent, talent, pedagogical abilities, communication abilities, didactic abilities, authoritarian ability, insightful ability.

INTRODUCTION

Achieving independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan set before institutions of public education the important task of forming citizens of a new democratic state. In our society, which is at the stage of socio-economic development, there is currently a problem of improving the training of qualified personnel for pedagogical universities, academic lyceums, vocational colleges, and schools in order to improve the activities of secondary schools. This requires paying great attention to training in higher educational institutions young specialists who meet the requirements of the time, not only with a deep study of theoretical knowledge, but at the same time with excellent human qualities, capable of going into business. and who have a thorough mastery of their work. Moreover, this requirement of the present time once again emphasizes the need to train future teachers as cultural individuals, armed with high pedagogical skills and technical skills. The years of independence are literally socio-economic and cultural for the Republic of Uzbekistan.determining development prospects,

carrying out large-scale reforms in order to take a worthy place among the countries of the world community. Studying the experience of developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, carrying out fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures the achievement of new achievements. Although established international cooperation in various fields has yielded results, strengthening national independence in all aspects, enriching the achievements achieved, and quickly eliminating existing shortcomings requires special dedication, enthusiasm, courage and determination from members of society.

MAIN CONCLUSIONS AND RESULTS

Teaching teaching first appeared in the mid-19th century. Desterverg was the first to talk about teaching skills and perceptual abilities and draw attention to this issue. He drew attention to the strength of pedagogical skill, pedagogical tact and rigor. Liberty. He put forward the concept of a teacher's ability to acquire knowledge. Then, in the second half of the 19th century, P. G. Redkin put forward the concept of "moral ability." This idea was continued by K. D. Ushinsky: "The most important way to educate a person is conviction, and a person's faith can only be influenced by conviction." L.N. Tolstoy said: "For education to be successful, people who educate must be able to educate themselves without stopping." Based on his experience, A. S. Makarenko says that "if everyone works hard, if he is demanding of himself, he can be a good teacher." Abilities are present in all people, and they are not the same, one has high, another has average and low. To work successfully, every teacher must have teaching skills. The owner of pedagogical skill spends little effort and achieves great results. Abilities appear and develop in the process of activity. Abilities are those psychological characteristics of a person on which knowledge, skills and abilities depend, but these characteristics themselves do not relate to this knowledge, skills and abilities. Human abilities are only the ability to acquire

knowledge and skills. Whether this knowledge and skills will be acquired or burdened depends on many circumstances. A child's musical ability does not guarantee that he will become a musician. For a child to become a musician, he must have a special education, perseverance, good health, a musical instrument, sheet music and other conditions. Without this, the ability may not develop and fade away. A serious mistake for a teacher would be to hastily draw a conclusion, without serious testing, that the student has the necessary skills and system of competencies, as well as solid knowledge and working methods. There are many people who were not recognized by others for their abilities as children and later became famous because of those abilities. Effective and successful organization of the pedagogical process depends on the pedagogical skill of the teacher. One source explains the concept of "ability" as follows: an individual psychological characteristic that makes it easy for a person to master any activity. Abilities are divided into two groups in the form of general and special abilities. "General abilities are manifested in the main types of personal activities, and special abilities are considered to be those that are manifested in certain types of professional activities (mathematical, technical, musical, visual arts, literature (poetry and prose), physical training, etc.). abilities... One of the leading characteristics of abilities is to creatively imagine the essence of things and events. Pedagogical abilities are properties that are important for ensuring the rational organization and conduct of pedagogical activities by the teacher, the effective implementation of practical tasks. The priority signs of pedagogical abilities are:

- pedagogical tact (the teacher's compliance with existing ethical principles and rules of conduct in communication with students, organized in various forms of activity,

- having the skills to correctly compare them);

- pedagogical observation (the teacher's ability to notice even the simplest

features characteristic of students);

- love for students (love them, show kindness to them, share your inner experiences, feelings, dreams, aspirations, take care of them in difficult situations);

- the need to transfer knowledge (as a teacher, he strives to transfer the knowledge he has to students)

F. N. Gonobolin considers it important for a teacher to demonstrate the following skills:

- ability to understand the student;- the ability to present materials that can be mastered by young, psychologically all students;

- ability to develop students' interests;

- organization skills;

- pedagogical tact;

- have the opportunity to see the results of your work, etc.

V. A. Krutetsky, generalizing the abilities inherent in a teacher, shows that their types are as follows

Main types

Didactic abilities – the ability to clearly, clearly and accessibly explain educational material, arouse students’ interest in subjects, and develop independent thinking skills.

Academic skills - mathematics, physics, biology, chemistry, native language, literature, history, etc. ability to master the basics of science

Perceptual abilities - the ability to penetrate into the inner world of a person, psychological observation, the ability to understand the subtleties associated with the student’s temporary mental states.

Speech abilities are a person’s ability to clearly and clearly express their feelings through speech, as well as facial expressions and pantomime. Organizational skills – the ability to organize a team of students, the

ability to unite a team, the ability to properly organize teaching activities.

Authoritarian ability is the ability to create the opportunity to gain authority among students by influencing them emotionally and voluntarily.

Communicative ability - the ability to communicate with students, find an effective way to communicate with them, the presence of pedagogical tact that connects mutual pedagogical communication in accordance with the goal.expressive ability. Even low hearing or lack of hearing cannot significantly impede the development of professional musical abilities. The problem of quantitative measurement of abilities in psychology has a long history. At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, a number of psychologists (Kettel, Theremin, Spearman, etc.) proposed determining students' abilities under the influence of requirements related to the need to make a career. choice of government specialties. Abilities can be general or special. By studying the specific psychological characteristics of various abilities, we discover that these abilities are not one, but many.It is possible to distinguish general qualities that meet the requirements of a given type of activity, and special qualities that meet somewhat narrower areas of this activity. In some people these general qualities are expressed in a Yorkian manner. For example, Ibn Sina was a doctor, writer, musician, mathematician, etc. Hamza Hakimzoda Niyazi was a playwright, poet, composer, teacher and public figure. For some people, virtues belong to specific activities. For example, the ability to draw, write, draw. A high level of development of abilities is called talent. Talent is a set of abilities that allows a person to successfully, independently and originally perform any complex work. Talent, like ability, consists of the ability to achieve a high level of creativity and significant success.

Here we are in first place in Uzbek wrestling and one of the first places in boxing. All these are wedges of time.Talent is the sum of abilities, their totality. An isolated, individual ability, even if it has reached a very high level of

development and is clearly expressed, cannot be equated with talent. Although the development of abilities depends on natural conditions, which are not necessarily the same among different people, the connection between talent goals and abilities mentioned above shows that abilities are not simply a gift of nature, but a product of personal history. If in animals the achievements of the previous generation are transmitted to the next generation mainly through hereditary morphological changes in the body, then humanity is realized in this socio-historical way, i.e. through craft, language, works of art, etc. A factor indicating whether a person's ability to perform a certain activity, whether he feels a burden or not, is considered a learning method. Where educational methodology is weak, there are claims that ability is key. It is common knowledge that the methodology is constantly being improved, which leads to a narrowing of the range of “key capabilities”. The problem of forming abilities and talents is of great social and national importance. Due to the fact that the structure of the totality of mental qualities realized as abilities is determined by a single and separate activity need, it is necessary to express this in a unique way for each type of activity. Interest is considered one of the important psychological aspects of personality, in which the individual character of a person is directly laid down. Curiosity directly plays an important role in people's worldviews, beliefs, ideals, that is, their highest goals, good intentions, dreams and hopes, and serves to ensure their success. on the level of knowledge. Curiosity, as a motive, creates a creative approach to various forms of activity to understand the wonderful aspects of existence, master the fundamentals of science, forms a responsible attitude to work and study, and creates psychological conditions for the formation of hard work and determination. , and the indomitable will in each individual person creates. When approaching, based on the psychological nature of interest, interest plays the role of desire, activity, internal motivation and source of need satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Thus, from the very beginning, when issues of personal education were put on the agenda for the development of human society, social demands were put forward regarding the formation of a category of persons responsible for the education and upbringing of children, their ability to meet certain requirements. social needs of both individuals and professionals, as well as to acquire professional skills. Introducing students to social needs, developing their pedagogical skills and professional skills is one of the important tasks. The basics of pedagogical skills are studied. Thus, the need to withstand strong competition in the labor market under market conditions encourages each specialist to develop professional competence and inherent qualities. In lexical terms it means “abilities,” and in substantive terms it means “effective use of theoretical knowledge in activities, the ability to demonstrate a high level of professional skills, abilities and talents.” In particular, on the basis of teacher-specific professional competence, such qualities as social, special (psychological, methodological, informational, creative, innovative and communicative), personal, technological and ultimate competence are reflected. A number of studies, in particular by A.K. Markova and B. Nazarova, note the structural foundations of pedagogical competence. Teacher's profession competence of the pedagogical (educational and educational) process effectively, ensures a successful organization. To acquire professional competence, a teacher must pay attention to consistent self-development. The “Individual Development Program” is useful for teachers in self-development. Indeed, in this program, the qualities of competence that the teacher possesses, and the qualities that need to be developed, BCM can be expressed clearly and objectively.

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